

SESSION 8

CULTURAL PRACTICES AND COMBINED CONTROL MEASURES

TUESDAY 11 SEPTEMBER 2018 18:00 - 19:45

OP39

Activity of the compost Bio Vegetal® in containing the soil-borne pathogen *Verticillium dahliae* (Kleb.)

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Verticillium dahliae Kleb. is a widely distributed soilborne pathogen, causing vascular wilt diseases in over 400 host plants and resulting in severe damage annually in different parts of the world. The pathogen survives in the soil for many years by producing melanised, thick-walled resting structures, called microsclerotia, which are resistant to environmental extremes and remain associated with organic and soil particles. The disease is difficult to control, due to production of microsclerotia and the localization of the pathogen within the xylem vessels during its parasitic phase.

In the past, the control of *Verticillium* wilt has relied on soil fumigation, but the use of methyl bromide, the main soil fumigant, was banned due to its devastating impact on the environment and soil living organisms. Currently, control is based mainly on preventive methods, and integrated disease management strategy. Among the different means available, the application of compost shows less or null detrimental impact on the environment. Besides the suppressive effect against plant diseases, composts improve soil health and structure, and stimulate the growth of soil microbiota. Bio Vegetal® is a fertilizer already available on the market and used as soil improver. Its source matrices are organic municipal wastes and green pruning residues, whose composting process is triggered by mesophilic and thermophilic microorganisms.

The objective of this work was to evaluate the activity of the commercial compost Bio Vegetal® on the soil-borne pathogen *V. dahliae*, by "in vitro" tests, on conidia and on microsclerotia, and in vivo experiments, using both soil with and without host plants (tomato and/or olive).

Inoculum density of *V. dahliae* microsclerotia occurring in the soil treated with Bio Vegetal® at different doses, either transplanted or not with tomato or olives, showed significantly lower values as compared to the untreated control. Similarly, results from in vitro test indicate a significant reduction of microsclerotia germination in the treatments amended with filter-sterilized aqueous extract of the compost Bio Vegetal. Further researches are in progress to determine the effect of Bio Vegetal® on the soil microbial community.